

THE STUDY OF THE PERSONALITY OF JALOLIDDIN MANGUBERDI IN HISTORICAL SOURCES

Ortikov Olim

Teacher of the Department of "Social and Economic Sciences" of Jizzakh branch of the National University of Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *This article scientifically analyzes the coverage of the personality of Jaloliddin Manguberdi in historical sources.*

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Jalaliddin khwarazmshah Alouddin Muhammad's first-born son by his wife, Oychechak, was consequently the rightful heir to the throne. When Jaloliddin Manguberdi came of age, his father appointed him governor and Crown Prince of lands as far as Ghazna, Bomiyan, Ghur, Bust, Takinabad, Zamindovar and Indian territories (1215). However, Muhammad Khwarazmshah's mother Turkon khotun and Qipjak emir were stripped of the succession in favor of Qutbiddin Özlüqshah, the youngest son of Muhammad Khwarazmshah, due to the persistent protests. Jalaliddin Manguberdi participated in his father's military campaigns, demonstrating that he was a brave warrior, a talented warlord. Turkon, deeply despised khotun Oychechak and his child, patronized his grandson Qutbiddin Özlükshah, who was born to his tribal and foster-daughter-in-law, in all respects. One incident in which nasawi naql arrived gives a vivid picture of the identity of Turkon khotun and his attitude towards his own grandson Jalaluddin.

Every Uzbek child of our first president "who were my ancestors, recorded the genesis of our Nation, How was the process of getting up on his feet, recovery, formation." [1] especially during the period of the mustabid regime, "... on what soils were the great names of Jalaliddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, Babur Mirzo and other great-grandfathers entangled?", repeatedly exclaiming that he had to ask himself. In this matter, the question "has a true history of Uzbekistan and the Uzbek people been created that is worth bringing to the general public today?" [2], and they argued that it was necessary to revise the history written on the basis of false ideas written by others during the time of the Psalms.

The historian writes that when Turkon khotun, who was in critical condition of the Mongol compression, was told about the strength of one of his retinue, Jalaliddin, and advised him to flee to his refuge, Turkon khotun replied: "Was it not my dependence on the favor of Oychechak's son? More than that, I prefer to be held captive in the hands of Chipgizkhan and my current humiliation!" Sources indicate that this princess, belonging to the qangli (according to some accounts, boyavut) tribe, acted at the level of a second ruler in the Khwarezmshah state, interfering in all the affairs of the kingdom.

Unable to overcome the successive failures, before the death of khwarezmshah Muhammad, who had gone to the Caspian Sea under enemy persecution, his mother Turkon rescinded her sentence after hearing that khotun had been captured by the Mughals, and gathered his sons Jalaliddin, Özlüqshah, and Eshah to state his will: "the kingdom ties were severed, the foundations of the state were emptied and collapsed. The goal of the GNOME is now obvious: he dusted the country with his nails and teeth. For me, only my son Manguberdi is able to take revenge on him (i.e., Ghanim). Therefore, I will appoint him crown prince, and you must obey him." [2]

After khwarazmshah's death the Prince returns to Urganch. But the supporters of Turkon khotun in the capital organize an assassination attempt against Jalaliddin. Warned in time by this, Jalaliddin leaves the city with 300 survivors accompanied by the governor of Khojand, Temur Malik.

He found many examples in history of the fact that the princes took advantage of their prestige and position or the turmoil that fell on the head of the country and raised their heads against their father or Agha-ini to usurp the throne. Jalaliddin, on the other hand, was able to renounce his legal right in the cause of the yurt's liberation as well, sacrificing his personal interests in the general interest.

All sons of khwarezmshah have enough such qualities ultimately to the non-existent-as a result, it can be said that it caused the destruction of them and the state of the Khwarezmshahs in general. Take, for example, Ghiyosiddin Pirshoh. When Jalaliddin lost his entire army in the Battle of the Sindh River and came to the lands under Pirshah to gather strength, he sent an army of 30,000 against his brother. The efforts of Pirshah's mother Beklaroy as well as Amir-larnig will be taken into account the war of the Brotherhood. Later, in 1228, on the eve of the upcoming important battle with the Mongols near the city of Isfahan, Pirshoh took his army and fled. In this battle, although Jalaliddin was victorious, this victory was won in exchange for a large calafot.

In fairness, it is worth noting that all the Sons of Khwarazmshah died with a candle in their hands, not smearing the honor of their household and high ranks. Özlükşah bilai Özgşah was brutally killed in an unequal battle. Rukniddin Ghursanchti, on the other hand, was captured at the Fortress of Columnavand (in Columnavand - an ancient city in the territory of present-day Iran) for 6 months, having thwarted the enemy and finally in the wake of a lack of madad. Ghursanchti preferred torture and death when Toymas Poyan, the Mongol warlord, demanded that he bow to his knees. Unlike Jalaliddin, only one important thing for these princes to fight the Ghanim with dignity seems to be a lack of high military genius. As long as Jalaliddin was given the necessary things for the work of the military, then what did he lack?

To give a worthy assessment of Jalaliddin Manguberdi's skill as a sergeant, it is necessary to correctly assess the military strength of the main enemy he fought against, namely the Mongols. In fairness, it is worth noting that the Chishizkhan army, made up of extraordinary militant Turko-Mongol-Tungusic tribes, which fully mastered the military art of the Northeast Asian settlers, which had not been equal for centuries, was an immodest large, powerful and terrible force beyond the scope of our usual taxi-yulot. The Mongols knew well what method or trick to use, given the location of the battle, the scarcity of the enemy and other factors, had also mastered the methods of besieging cities throughout the war in China and recruited Chinese masters who knew how to make and use siege weapons for their services. When they fought, they fought with an awe, or rather, punishments, and panicked with their fierce actions and various exclamations. It is necessary to admit, the enemy was brave and persistent. According to Ibn ad-Asir's account, while a Mongol soldier was being held captive, he threw himself off his horse and hit his bopti hard on a large rock, killing John will surrender.

At the moment, the potential of the Peoples holding the borders of Turon in the chapter of azmu shijoati, military skill to the time when the issue of the yurt protection, erk and freedom is being resolved, is also well known from history. But if only a mighty guide can be found in the secrets of the war, who can follow men to him. Jalaliddin Manguberdi was such a guide.

Jaloliddin Manguberdi minted silver and copper coins in his name in India, which was read in the tobe Indian estates with the name attached to Khutba. However, the situation was getting more and more complicated. It is revealed that Eltutmish, Qubacha, as well as other provincial governors of India are conspiring with each other to form an alliance against Jalaliddin Manguberdi. The two warlords of jalaliddin Manguberdi, Yazidak pahlavon and Sunqurjiq Toysi, also treacherously side with Eltutmish. To get rid of the difficult situation, Jalaliddin Manguberdi calls a military council. Many of the emirs march towards Iraq at a time of political parochialism in Iraq, offering to seize it from Ghiyosiddin Pirshah. Jalaliddin Manguberdi leaves Uzbek Toy Jahan Pahlavon to his conquered possessions in India and Hasan Qarluq to Ghur and Ghazni provinces as a viceroy and heads to Iraq.

As Chulu crosses the biobones, many of Jaloliddin Manguberdi's Warriors die, and he finally arrives in Kirman with 4,000 Warriors. Ghiyosiddin expresses tobelik to Khojib Jalaliddin Manguberdi, the Viceroy of Pirshah in Kirman. After that, Jaloliddin Manguberdi comes to Sheroz, the center of the Persian region. The Persian governor sa'd ibn Zangiye h and the Yazd governor Alouddavla ibn Tughanshah give him a Tobe. When Jaloliddin Manguberdi comes to Isfahan, the population greets him with great pomp, his army is supplied with armor. This is not to the liking of Ghiyosiddin Pirshah, who sets out against his brother with an army of 30,000 cavalry. However, Jaloliddin Manguberdi sends Odek as ambassador with gifts to him and resolves the dispute peacefully. The chief of the force, Jaloliddin, sided with Manguberdi.[3]

Despite his high hand in a series of battles with them, he realized that it was difficult to establish an important settlement in India, to find allies, and from there he came to Iran, and in 1224 to Azerbaijan and conquered it. At this time, the activities of e'taboran Jaloliddin in the territories of Azerbaijan and neighboring countries (Iran, Georgia, Kohnya, Anatolia, Iraq and other arab countries) begin.

In May 1225, Jaloliddin Manguberdi captured Marogha without a fight. The governors of Damascus, Erbil, however, agree to ally with him. Uzbek left Tabriz and fled to ganja, then to Alinjo Castle, where he died. Jaloliddin Manguberdi marries Princess khotun. After a few days in Tabriz, he starts his army towards Georgia. In August 1225, near Garni Castle, chief Ivane Mkhargrdzeli of the gurjis led an army of 60,000 men to tor-mor and marched towards Tiflis. The Georgian Queen Rusudana moves to Kutaisi. Jaloliddin Manguberdi occupies Dvin, Lori, with the governor of Surmari stating his tobeism.

Historians write that on the eve of the war, Shalva (gurji's most powerful army leader) peshed his army, which he had knocked down when he welcomed an envoy of the opposing side, saying: "at this moment, in my time, I would like amir al-mouminin Ali (ibn Abu Talib hazrat Ali, the fourth caliph) to be alive. Then I would show him what power would be like, he would forget the Battle of Badr and the Battle of Khaibar". On the basis of this boasting of Shalva, the Battle of Badr took place — in March 624, Muhammad (P.624).a.v.) provided for a battle of struggle for the religion of Islam by supporters. This struggle paved the way for the widespread spread of Islam in the Arabian Peninsula. Khaybar is an oasis located between Medina and Damascus. In 628, Muhammad (s.a.v.) was conquered by. It is said that hazrat Ali showed unique courage in both battles.[4]

In 1231, shortly before Jalaliddin's death, when the Mongols invaded Azerbaijan, Jalaliddin sent a chopper to the rulers of neighboring countries, addressing: "the armies of the Moorish-malakhic beadad tatar (i.e., Mongol) are approaching, of which the iya fortress and neither cities

will survive. This is to take fear and exclamation from them in the hearts of the Warriors of the parties. When I went out of there, you did not have the opportunity to resist them. Have mercy on yourself, your children, and all the Muslims, and each of you send me a unit with the flag, and give me encouragement, and if my vine reaches the voice of Union and harmony among us, they will be depressed and our soldiers will be disappointed." [5]

As mentioned above, no one extended a helping hand to Jalaliddin. And the result of this is well known.

Well, there is a model worthy of aspiration in the vibrant, meaningful life and activities of Jalaliddin Manguberdi, and at the same time a huge lesson that will never lose its relevance.

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